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Revealing the role of edges in the electrocatalytic synthesis of H₂O₂ over metal-free nanocarbon

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Designing efficient metal-free electrocatalysts for the synthesis of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) requires identifying precisely the reaction mechanism. Reporting in *Matter*, Lin et al. showcase the role of edges by using molecular nanocarbon models. Time-resolved spectroscopy, combined with simulation studies and kinetic isotope experiments, indicates that the rate-determining step is the formation of the superoxide anion O₂^{-•} deriving from one-electron transfer to the end-on chemisorbed O₂.

The electrocatalytic synthesis of H₂O₂ is a relevant reaction for the development of the new e-chemistry,¹ e.g., a chemical production based on the use of renewable energy rather than derived from the use of fossil fuels. H₂O₂ is an intermediate in the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), but requires two rather than four electrons. This allows for having a lower overpotential (e.g., better energy efficiency) and a faster kinetic than in the case of ORR. H₂O₂ is a clean oxidant with a range of valuable uses in the chemical industry (from propylene oxide to caprolactam and aromatic hydroxylation industrial syntheses, to the area of pulp/paper bleaching and textile treatment) as well as in the environmental area of water and soil treatment.² The electrocatalytic synthesis of H₂O₂ was studied for many years, but a large academic and industrial research interest was restarted in the last few years.²⁻⁶ Recent studies emphasize the role of metal-free carbon materials,³⁻⁶ even if their properties in the H₂O₂ synthesis are known.⁷ However, their precise synthesis and better mechanistic understanding allowed to enhance their performances recently in terms of both selectivity and productivity. Metal-free carbon materials present the advantages of avoiding possible metal leaching, and thus potentially provide more stable

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performances, and lower costs. In environmental applications, where even traces of metals may be critical, avoiding the presence of metals in the electrocatalyst is crucial. Notwithstanding the growing research, the nature of the active sites and reaction mechanism is still a matter of debate. The problem is the presence of many types of possible active sites in nanocarbons, from edges sites to strained C-C bonds, different defects, heteroatoms (O, N, B, etc.) in different locations, and single metal atoms (or small metal clusters) deriving from impurities present in the source material to prepare the nanocarbon. Often a full characterization of the presence and amount of all these different active centres is missing and anyway difficult to realize.

The path to form H_2O_2 from chemisorbed O_2 may occur via different mechanisms, such as the first step of electron transfer to give the superoxide anion $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$, or via the first protonation of oxygen (OOH^*). Sequential electron and proton transfer may occur, or instead of a proton-assisted electron transfer, with sequential or simultaneous multi-electron- and proton- mechanism. O_2 chemisorption may be *side-* or *end-on*. The paths depend on both catalysts and pH which changes with the progress of the reaction. The nature of the triple-phase boundary at the electrocatalyst is crucial for performance, and modifications in the electrocatalyst change also this aspect. The diffusion of species and intermediate in negatively charged materials is still largely unknown. These are some of the open, highly interconnected questions in H_2O_2 electrosynthesis, only in part typically considered and that make challenging the understanding of the reaction mechanism and the comparison of the results. It is thus necessary to proceed by simplifying this complexity and isolating specific aspects which then may allow a better understanding of the overall mechanistic picture.

Reporting in *Matter*, Lin et al. showcase the role of edges by using molecular nanocarbon models.⁸ They studied the H_2O_2 synthesis over ten polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) to mimic the real zigzag and armchair edges of carbon materials and to investigate their role in the reaction mechanism. The performances of these electrocatalysts are enough good to allow obtaining reliable mechanistic data, with high selectivity to H_2O_2 (initially ~90%, but decreasing to ~60% in about 6h in a flow cell) and productivity. A current density in the 40-55 $\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ range was reported, which is good but in the range of those reported by other authors showing values up to about five times higher with comparable selectivities.⁹ The author's claim of theoretically mass activities "far exceed reported state-of-the-art catalysts" is thus not fully proven, even if a "theoretical activity" cannot be compared with experimental results.

In analysing the series PAHs, going from the simpler (phenanthrene with three fused aromatic rings) to the more complex having 50 fused aromatic rings, the size of the molecules and number of outer carbon atoms increases, changing also the electronic character (gradual decrease of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital - LUMO - and highest occupied molecular orbital - HOMO - energies with increasing the size of the π -conjugated system) and armchair and zigzag configuration. The activity (current density) is linearly correlated with all these aspects. Figure 1 reports, as an example, the linear correlation observed between specific activity and the number of exposed benzene units (NE) or the longitudinal size of PAHs. On the right of Figure 1, the different PAHs used and whether they show an armchair, a zigzag or a mixed configuration.

Figure 1 Correlations among the number of exposed benzene units (NE), the longitudinal sizes of PAHs and the specific activity in O_2 reduction per outer carbon atom in PAHs at $0.6 V_{RHE}$. Based on the data reported by Li et al.⁸

These results were interpreted as indicating that both armchair and zigzag edge sites are beneficial to the formation of H_2O_2 . However, other interpretations are also possible. In fact, by supporting the PAHs over a conductive substrate (carbon nanotube treated at $2400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to obtain a well-graphitized structure and extremely low defect ratio) Li et al. found that the mass activity increases by three orders of magnitude,⁸ evidencing that electron transport was the limiting factor in unsupported PAHs performances and the increase of the number of aromatic rings in the molecule likely increases the electronic conductivity.

Li et al. also reported time-resolved spectroscopic evidence and simulation calculation of the adsorbed intermediate product to support the mechanistic indications.⁸ They used in situ attenuated total reflectance infrared (ATR-IR) spectra for monitoring the dynamic evolution of the involved intermediate oxygen species. The difficulty in studying carbon materials by infrared spectroscopy is well known, but the intensity of the signals detected is comparable to the background and also isotopic labelling results do not provide unequivocal indications. It is thus better to consider Li et al. as indications of the reaction mechanism, rather than a full proof of it. Li et al. conclusions are that the O₂ (ads) and O₂^{*} species as important intermediate products formed both at armchair and zigzag, while infrared signs for OOH* species were not detected. It must be remembered that the absence of detection does not necessarily imply that the species do not form or is not intermediate. The species detected are those less reactive and which thus accumulate over the surface of the electrocatalysts in a sufficient amount to allow their detection.

Time-resolved ATR analysis on chrysene (CY) and naphthacene (NT), representing only armchair or zigzag configurations for PAHs, shows that the infrared position of O₂ (ads) peak at 1398 cm⁻¹ does not change with the time of experiments and the nature of PAH, while that of O₂^{*} decreases from 1163 cm⁻¹ to 1150 cm⁻¹ in CY, and from 1206 cm⁻¹ to 1190 cm⁻¹ in NT also after about 20s of time on stream. The intensity of the infrared signals of both O₂ (ads) and O₂^{*} increases with time on stream, in the first ten seconds of time on stream, with slight differences in time to reach a constant value depending on the oxygen species and type of PAH. However, the high error in these measurements may question the reliability of the conclusions. Li et al. interpreted these results as a sign of the different kinetics of the process.⁸ However, they determined the surface process of accumulation of adsorbed species which is not related to the reaction kinetics of the electrocatalytic process. Li et al. interpreted the initial red-shift of O₂^{*} species as due to “the steric hindrance between the adsorbed O₂^{*} and the generation of the follow-up OOH species from O₂^{**}”. However, a diffusion-limited behaviour was instead likely observed as typically occurring in ATR cells, and thus not related to a true (e.g., not mass-transfer limited) kinetic behaviour.

Li et al. finally reported kinetic isotope experiments (KIE) to determine the rate-determining step (RDS) using KOD rather than KOH electrolyte. Although this provides some indications for the steps involving H-containing species, the RDS in the electron transfer to chemisorbed O₂

does not involve H-species. Thus, experiments with labelled $^{17}\text{O}_2$ would be necessary. In addition, KIE data on the differences between KOD and KOH experiments were inside the experimental error. However, theoretical calculations support the conclusions.

In conclusion, we have analysed the Li et al. results⁸ showing that together with interesting aspects there are various open questions requiring further studies and perhaps more sophisticated experimental techniques. However, the use of precise model carbon materials can be of great support to limit the number of variables and should be used to understand also the role of other characteristics of nanocarbon materials (strained bonds, defects, functional groups due to heteroatoms, etc.) which can play a relevant role in H_2O_2 synthesis.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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